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Research Article

LIVER AND DIABETES: A VICIOUS CIRCLE¹Dr Muhammad Shakeel Khan, ²Dr Fawad Ullah, ³Dr Azmatullah
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Abstract:

Recently, the complicated relationship between liver and diabetes has gained immense importance. The chief pathogenic determinant in diabetes and fatty liver is insulin resistance. Hypothalamus, intestinal microbiome, inflammation, and white adipose tissues also play a significant role in defining this link of the liver and diabetes. The initiator of systemic insulin resistance is the hepatocyte insulin resistance that also depicts the danger of fatty acids. The body's stress response in the form of apoptosis, lipotoxicity, endoplasmic reticular stress, and lipofautophagy are all linked with the above-mentioned relationship. Various biochemical pathways and risk factors support type 2 diabetes in the development of progressive liver disease, like cirrhosis, liver cancer, and non-alcoholic steatohepatitis. This circular pathway which leads to liver disease towards type 2 diabetes, and type 2 diabetes to liver disease is a vicious cycle.

After searching multiple sources and clinical examination, this review paper is compiled with critical analysis, which throws significant light upon the development of type 2 diabetes in patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. Moreover, the detrimental effects of type 2 diabetes in the liver are also discussed.

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INTRODUCTION:

Type 2 Diabetes is also known as T2D. It is characterized by dyslipidemia and hyperglycemia developed by Islet β -cells. These cells are unable to secrete an adequate insulin amount in the blood. As this anomaly is owing to a varying degree of insulin resistance (IR) in genetically predisposed people, so this puts an immense burden upon societies. Studies have found a link between 'hepatogeneous diabetes' and cirrhotics. Patients with T2D, impaired life expectancy, are not only exposed to vascular complications and end-stage renal diseases, but they can also be subjected to hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) and cirrhosis.^{1,2} Moreover, deep insight has also revealed that the most common liver disorder, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) lays down various pathways that lead to T2D via IR. This paper throws light upon these linkages and how they impact each other.³

From Fatty Liver to Diabetes

- **Mutual Pathogenesis of Diabetes and NAFLD**

It is found that primary NAFLD is not just responsible for clinical constellation embracing hypertension, T2D, obesity, atherogenic dyslipidemia, but it also promotes the development of metabolic syndrome (MS). Specific endocrine derangements in some patients also lead to secondary NAFLD development.⁴

- **IR and the Fatty Liver**

It was proposed that IR and fatty liver is based on the 'two-hit hypothesis'. In this, the first one is the accumulation of triglycerides and steatosis due to systemic IR. The second hit is in the form of hepatic oxidative stress which is thought to be the result of long-term triglyceride storage.⁵ Owing to such stress, imbalance between oxidized equivalents and glutathione, dysfunctional β -oxidation of fatty acids, and impaired mitochondrial energy production results in hepatocyte injury occurs due to free radicals and lipid peroxidation products that directly disrupts cell organelles and membranes. These events lead to apoptosis or necrotic cell death as well as boost up inflammatory mediators.⁶

Studies have shown that the first hit stage can precede the fatty liver development in humans followed by a refined second hit stage. In another 'multiple parallel-hit hypotheses', it was elaborated that multiple contributions as from gut, adipose tissues and extrahepatic tissues can cause the development of liver inflammation, which then causes cirrhosis, steatosis, and HCC.^{7,8}

The liver plays a key role in lipid metabolism and regulating glucose, anomalies in both these steps cause T2D and NAFLD. Fasting hyperglycemia,

when the person is having T2D, results due to unopposed endogenous glucose production, and hyperglycemia due to IR and an inability to store glucose as glycogen after a meal.

- **Role of Intestinal Microbiome in IR**

The natural bacterial flora in the intestine plays a significant defensive role to combat host defense and regulate innate immune functioning. Any unnecessary change in this microbiome leads to impaired host defenses which ultimately results in increased paracellular intestinal permeability, an etiologic factor in inflammation, production of tumor necrosis (TNF), lipopolysaccharide and impaired liver, skeletal muscle, and adipose tissue functioning. Another well-contributing factor in hepatocyte triglyceride and excessive fatty acid storage is a high level of free fatty acid (FFA) secretion from WAT, this all results in exacerbation of hepatic IR.⁹

- **Skeletal and Cardiac Muscle**

Insulin resistance not just effects the liver, but also impairs the ability of skeletal and cardiac muscles in glucose transport as fuel by inhibiting Glut4 transporter. This impairment of glucose uptake by muscle cells and adipocytes, storage of FFA and impaired release from cells perpetuates peripheral IR.¹⁰

- **Hepatocyte IR**

In addition to the role of white adipose tissues, microbiome, inflammation, and adipocytokines contribute significantly to hepatocyte IR.¹¹ Diet and exercise are also crucially involved. After a carbohydrate rich meal consumption, physical activity reduces muscle IR, hepatic de novo lipogenesis, and synthesis of hepatic triglyceride. However, a poor diet can leave negative impacts.¹² For instance, high consumption of lipogenic sugar fructose is linked with MS, NAFLD, IR, and NASH. Smoking also favors fibrotic progression and hepatic lipogenesis in NAFLD and the development of T2D.

Intake of dairy products can improve the glycolipid metabolic profile and diabetes prevention via increased Trans-palmitoleate serum levels. Insulin signaling is inhibited in the human liver by hepatic protein kinase C (PKC) isoforms which promotes hepatocyte IR.¹³ Antisense oligonucleotide (ASO) against PKCs showed improved MS parameters with a proper reduction in hepatocyte IR, fasting plasma insulin concentrations and intrahepatic triglycerides. Molecular explanation revealed that insulin receptor substrate-2 (IRS-2) phosphorylation and protein- serine-threonine kinase activity is restored by PKCs ASO.¹⁴ Another study showed that hepatic diglycol content founded in cytoplasmic lipid droplets was linked with the activation of hepatic PKCs activity, and was responsible for 64% of fluctuating insulin sensitivity.

- **Fatty Acids**

A concept evolved based on different studies that triglycerides can serve as a protective reservoir in NAFLD pathogenesis.¹⁵ Endoplasmic reticulum is responsible for folding and assembling the vast majority of proteins, that are secreted by cells and displayed on their surfaces. Only properly assembled and folded proteins can leave the cell and advance towards its surface. So, in order to maintain this function properly, the cell regulates the ER protein folding capacity as per requirement.¹⁶ Intracellular signal transduction pathways are activated, which are also known as unfolded protein response, when a burden of un-assembled and unfolded proteins is placed in the lumen of ER (ER stress). Researches when went through the in-depth study of hepatocyte cells with specific fatty acid content.¹⁷ It was found that saturated fatty acids like stearate, oleate, and palmitate resulted in mediating extra ER stress that increased hepatocyte apoptosis and cell death.¹⁸

From T2D to Progressive Liver Disease

Previously it is shown that how potential mechanisms of NAFLD can be linked with T2D in individuals with long term hepatic IR. Now, below it is explained how T2D can induce progressive liver damage.¹⁹

- **Fibrogenesis**

Interestingly, it is found that atherogenesis and fibrosis in the liver might go parallel to each other. Due to obesity and TNF- α , expression of plasminogen activator inhibitor 1 (PAI-1) increases that can lead to impaired fibrinolysis, hepatic fibrosis, and development of atherosclerosis. WAT is also found playing a negative role in hepatic fibrosis in NASH.²⁰

The greater insulin resistance one person has, the higher the induced apoptosis he will face. Apoptosis is induced by FFA, the key histological feature of NASH and it correlates with inflammatory fibrotic changes. The NASH induced apoptosis in the key associator for liver injury and liver fibrosis.²¹

- **Hepatic Carcinogenesis**

Hepatocellular carcinoma is the primary known liver cancer and is the third leading cause of death by cancer and ranks fourth among the most prevalent malignancies. In most of the cases, HCC occurs due to complications created by infections, which are caused by hepatitis virus B or C.

Various mechanisms like abnormal glucose metabolism, hepatocyte iron deposition, advanced fibrosis, and age, favors the development of hepatocellular carcinoma followed by NAFLD. The sub-clinical inflammation affiliated with steatosis, IR, unbalanced adipocytokine ratio and oxidative ratio, (i.e. increased IL-6, decreased

adiponectin, and leptin TNF- α) can all participate in DNA damage and cell growth kinetics which make the environment favorable for the HCC development.

Two main enzyme family pathways, tensin homolog (PTEN) / Akt axis and phosphoinositide 3- kinase (PI3K)/ phosphatase are key regulators of some crucial cellular functions like different growth factors signaling, insulin signaling, cell survival, glycolipidic homeostasis, and apoptosis. In this pathway, the PI3K signaling feature is terminated by PTEN acting as a phosphoinositide phosphatase via PtdIns (3, 4, 5) p(3) and dephosphorylating PtdIns (3, 4) P(2). PTEN is not only dysregulated in obesity, T2D, and IR but is also a tumor suppressor. Therefore, it represents an ideal metabolic pathway which leads to the development of HCC under many metabolic disorders like T2D, IR, and NAFLD. It has been found that antidiabetic drug is helpful in modifying the risk of HCC development.

CONCLUSION:

Clinical trials and detailed studies have shown pathways that lead from fatty liver to diabetes type 2 development and pathways that lead to diabetes type 2 to fatty liver disease and injury in predisposed individuals. However, when T2D has fully developed its roots in the human body, it will not only contribute to steatogenesis, but also participates in progressive liver damage, cirrhosis, NASH, HCC, and multiple diseases linked with other organs like heart and kidneys.

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